

EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE: KEY FOUNDATION FOR A NEW ECO-CENTERED PARADIGM

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ABSTRACT

The effects of climate change have ceased to be a mere prediction for the future. The intensification of extreme weather events, their abrupt consequences, and the increasing vulnerability to their harmful effects, has brought adaptation to climate change to the forefront of the public agenda. Traditionally, adaptation has been understood to include 'hard' infrastructure measures, and 'soft' actions. However, the challenges posed to our communities have demonstrated to go well beyond their psychological and emotional preparedness to cope with them. This article aims at highlighting the importance of emotional adaptation to the effects of climate change as a tool for comprehending the changes that are occurring, cope with them, and then build a new kind of relationship with the environment. The article argues that emotional adaptation, fostered through art and cultural identity strengthening, is a useful means for achieving long-term sustainability by appealing to a profound and structural behavioural transformation.

KEYWORDS: *climate change, adaptation, emotional adaptation, cultural agency, art, symbolism, cultural identity*

INTRODUCTION

The traditional definition of adaptation to climate change has its merits and limitations. The IPCC has defined adaptation as the '[a]djustment in natural or human systems to a new or changing environment. (...) [It] refers to adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities' (IPCC, 2001). According to the World Bank (2013), "Hard" adaptation measures usually imply the use of specific technologies and actions involving capital goods, such as dikes, seawalls and reinforced buildings, whereas "soft" adaptation measures focus on information, capacity building, policy and strategy development, and institutional arrangements'. When analyzed against a broad understanding of the Earth's systems as being interconnected in a complex web of relationships, where the human societies are part of a wider, unified system, the traditional definition of adaptation falls short in understanding the range of actions that are needed to cope with climate change.

In fact, those usually called 'hard' or 'soft' adaptation actions can be better understood as being part of a wide spectrum,

which includes both the human and the non-human lead actions aimed at coping with the effects to climate change, from variations in the structure (and infrastructure) of the systems, and changes in behavioral patterns.

Mind-shifts are fundamental to be able to cope with the impact of climate change. The purpose of this text is to put forward the concept of *emotional adaptation* to climate change as part of these sorts of actions. Departing from a concrete experience carried on at 'Las Delicias' water stream in Bogotá, Colombia, we have attempted to better understand processes where a community changes its behavioural patterns, as well as its emotional relationship with the surrounding ecosystem.

For this purpose, this paper starts by defining the concept of emotional adaptation (section one); it then addresses the case study of 'Las Delicias' in order to see how emotional adaptation was reflected in this community-based project (section two), and finishes with some concluding remarks on the utility of this concept for communities and their relationship to the environment (section three).

EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION AND THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE COMMUNITY AND THE ECOSYSTEM

A crucial factor for achieving long-term sustainability is developing emotional adaptation strategies that appeal to a profound and structural behavioural transformation. Our proposal of emotional adaptation emphasizes the experiential and imaginative level in the community-based work, thus building robust cultural changes that create a sustainable relationship with the surrounding ecosystem.

Emotional adaptation to climate change is defined here as the transformational process of achieving the awareness of the climate change phenomenon that is visibly occurring, comprehending, and experiencing psychological and emotional preparedness to these radical changes, and gaining a new perception of the relationship of humans to their environment, while considering one's self as an organic part of the ecosystem. Emotional adaptation is fundamental to understanding the effects of climate change, building the resilience to cope with it, and then building a new kind of relationship with the environment where communities see themselves as players of a broader system where close and harmonic interaction with the overall system itself is necessary for survival and well being.

The territories, landscapes, and climate system (atmosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, and geosphere, and their interactions) are crucial for human survival and subsistence, but are also vital because they are the frameworks in which cultural identity is anchored. The changes that occur to the climate system affect the landscape and socio-economic scheme and as a consequence the cultural realm of the communities is deeply impacted.¹ In this context a deep understanding and interpretation of what is happening is required to cope with the changes and anchor the cultural identity of the community to the reality of a changing place with a sense of belonging.

In Larry Robinson's words, '[a]s human beings we have a need for place – where we can be connected to a community of people, plants, animals and the land. Without this, we feel lost, alone and alienated. The world also needs us to belong to it since it is only when we inhabit a place that we care for it and assume responsibility for it. If we regard the world as only a place we are visiting, we have little interest in protecting it' (Burzell & Chalquist, 2009, p.29).

Cultural identity plays a key role as it directly contributes to the construction of our reality. We need to feel part of the context in which our livelihood is embedded as a previous step to protecting an ecosystem with a sense of ownership and belonging. In this context, the creation and appropri-

1 In its Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) the IPCC re-confirmed that climate change has affected many physical and biological systems (IPCC 2014). Based on its observations, it concluded that 'changes in climate have caused impacts on natural and human systems on all continents and across the oceans. Evidence of climate-change impacts is strongest and most comprehensive for natural systems'.

tion of narratives about the surrounding reality is fundamental. 'Stories can inflame the imagination. Stories about our families and ancestors, stories about trees and animals and rocks around us, stories about the stars and planets and gods can help find and remember our place and anchor us in time and space. In re-storying the world, we can restore it' (Burzell & Chalquist, 2009, p.29).

A crucial element of the cultural identity, as one of the routes for emotional adaptation, is the ritualism and mysticism that surrounds each culture, which is the spinal cord for the cosmogony of people's lives. It permits having a mindset that facilitates acquiring an understanding of the world and the person's place in it. The existence of a strong cultural identity that includes a particular ritualism and mysticism can be understood as a fundamental tool to achieve emotional adaptation to climate change. The relevance of symbols and myths has been highlighted by Mircea (1991, p.62) when he explains that '[t]o transcend profane time and re-enter into mythical great time is equivalent to a revelation of ultimate reality that is strictly metaphysical, and can be approached in no other way through myths and symbols'. Emotional adaptation is at the crossroads between the need to gain physical contact with nature that can contribute to recovering an inner ritualistic practice, and the creation of stronger relationships with the environment that foster the adoption adaptive practices involving the community and the ecosystem.

As this inner process occurs, an intuitive understanding is triggered that makes us realize that affecting nature is equivalent to affecting one's self. Through that process, a broader transformation detonates. This is why structural behavioural changes can only be achieved if they come from within each person and from within the community rather than through indoctrination processes where 'green' actions are made in automated and repetitive ways without a reflexive process behind them. Part of the strength of *emotional adaptation* processes is the recognition that the climate change effects we are experiencing are part of a bigger complex system. In this system, humans are agents capable of finding solutions, and are an integral part of the system that is being threatened by climate change.

In this context, art has a crucial role as an emotional medium and creator of symbolism. Art as a bridge, a new language that establishes deep communication between nature and the individuals, is a vehicle to generate a sense of belonging and environmental awareness to guarantee sustainability and recovery of ecosystems. As the artist David Buckland states: 'There is a need to shift our mental and physical state from observation to habitation. This is artistic territory; it is what artists do – they uncover the hidden, the unpalatable, the unstated, whether it be in love, ethics or values (...)' (Buckland & Wainwright, 2010, p.8). During the case study conducted as part of our research, collaborative community art installations functioned as a bridge that encouraged community 'dialogue' with the ecosystem understood as a *living being*.

The experience carried out at ‘Las Delicias’ water stream allowed us to better understand processes where a community changes its behavioural patterns and emotional relationship with its surrounding ecosystem, and to observe how this served as an adaptation tool that fostered further adaptation actions carried forward with the ecosystem. The following section focuses on this case study.

EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION AT ‘LAS DELICIAS’ WATER STREAM

Edward O. Wilson, a Harvard University scientist and Pulitzer Prize-winning author, defines biophilia as ‘the urge to filiate with other forms of life. (...) He and his colleagues argue that humans have an innate affinity for the natural world, probably a biologically based need integral to our development as individuals. In short, we need experiences in nature more than we know’ (Burzell & Chalquist, 2009, page no.207). In the same line of thought, the renamed eco-therapist Richard Louv, has explored how one of the reasons that we are experiencing a great disconnect with nature is the growing gap between culture and nature on the psyches of humans, especially children, and coins the term ‘nature deficit disorder’, which can be overcome through the deep experience and contact with nature (Louv, 2008).

Our research has focused on the space for bridging that gap, as a strategy for emotional adaptation to climate change. For this reason, the case study conducted at ‘Las Delicias’ stream focused on the use of ‘cultural agency’² through art as a means to increase the sense of belonging of the community to the ecosystem, and to foster the start of a behavioral change to transform its engagement with its surrounding habitat. Through this exercise we were able to see how individuals adopted greener and more harmonic attitudes aimed at the conservation of their neighboring ecosystem.

The initial artistic intervention that inspired this research was carried out in September 2011.³ With the support of the Bogotá city administration, in particular the environment district office, and Conservation International, an artistic intervention that was carried out in the context of a project to recover the ‘Las Delicias’ water stream. Its purpose was to increase the level of awareness and ownership in the surrounding community, using art as a means to do it. In this context, the project gathered a group of artists from the community itself, as well as a broader group of artists from Bogotá interested in environmental issues.

The community’s testimonies were recorded, and along with the media coverage and the high level of engagement of col-

laborators of different disciplines and industries, the case study demonstrated how various kinds of artistic languages were successful at encouraging the community to communicate with their neighboring ecosystem and re-build a deep relationship with it. More than 200 people from the community of ‘Bosque Calderon’, ‘Castillo’, and ‘Chapinero Alto’ neighbourhoods, the three surrounding neighborhoods of ‘Las Delicias’ stream, were engaged during the process.

The testimonies demonstrate the process of behavioural change that took place under an emotional adaptation process. A good example of this is Benedicto Galindo’s words, a community member and leader living near the stream, who expressed how moved he was by his daughter’s sudden interest in the stream after years of apathy:

For sure today important impacts occurred. My daughter, who is a physician, has never been interested in the stream, neither walking over the bank nor helping me in taking care of it, and today she was really present. Last night when I was writing the poem I recited today, she got near me and asked me what I was doing. I explained it to her, and she asked me if she could recite the poem on the ‘stage’ for me. To me, seeing her today walking over the stream’s bank after all these years of complete apathy moves me a lot. Outcomes will become more tangible in long-term, but be sure that there will be important outcomes.⁴

Testimonies of the members of the collective of artists that participated in the project also reconfirm how the artistic experience worked as a powerful transformational tool. The following are some examples of the artistic interventions that were carried out as part of the project.

Example One: Three Musicians, Mariposa Solar, Pedro Crump, and Héctor Buitrago, created music dedicated to the positive vibrations the water was making over the environment.

Hector Buitrago, a musician from “CONECTOR Cantoalagua de Aterciopelados”, stated that

Figure 1. Hector Buitrago honouring water through singing. Photo By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

2 We use the term ‘cultural agency’ in the sense described by Doris Sommer (Sommer, 2006) which relates to ‘a variety of public practices that link creativity with social contributions’.

3 A complete account of the project from September 2011 can be found at <http://artasabridge.wordpress.com/case-study/>.

4 All testimonies have been translated from Spanish to English by the authors, procuring to keep translations as literal as possible.

The art for awakening the hearts of people that are living nearby the ecosystems and that maybe do not have that awareness, is the most powerful tool for opening those hearts and the consciences so that we can again reconnect with the ancestral spirits that live in these places.

Pedro Crump, another musician participating, expressed:

One way of creating awareness is saying things, but through art and the human expression is (...) maybe stronger, it reaches more people to their hearts.

Example Two: Ecological Murals: Urban Collective Art (Doble C y WAP) and Gladys Ortiz, using environmentally safe aerosol paint and environmentally safe paint respectively, composed two large-scale murals.

The artists testified to the impact of their intervention. Danilo Ochoa, illustrator and graffiti artist from the 'Artes Urbanas' crew, and an inhabitant neighborhood Bosque Calderón, stated:

From art you can sensitize, you can make an appropriation of spaces, appropriation of territories, one part of appropriation is making you feel the owner of this [nature] without being the unique owner but with a responsibility for taking care of it.

Figure 2. Mural in Process

Figure 3. Final Mural Photos By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Figure 4. Graffiti artist - WAP. Photo By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Example Three: The renowned Colombian artist, Alfonso Ariza, inspired by the drawings of 40 neighborhood children on the river above, created a mosaic 60 square meters wide by the bank of the creek.

In Ariza's words:

Raising the awareness of the preservation of resources is creating awareness of the wildlife that exists, the flora that exist in every region and also raising awareness of the esthetical part, of how you can do something esthetical with recycled materials.

Figure 5.1 Neighborhood Children artists, Alfonso Ariza (Artist) and Santiago Aparicio V (Creative Director)

Figure 5.2 Mosaic detail. Photos By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Figure 6. Community member cropping native tree over the riverside. Photo By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Figure 7. Recycle tree under construction process. Photo By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Figure 8. Minimal Gallery Exhibition. Photo by: Santiago Aparicio V.

Example Four: Community Reforestation: The community planted 300 native trees over the bank of the creek, each one was given a God mother or God father committed to taking care of them.

Example Five: Recycle Trees⁵: The artist, Reynaldo Tibaduiza created structures with recycled material picked that day by the community from the stream and turned them into trees with the aim of creating symbolic significance that give dimension to this problem.

This first artistic intervention of 2011 created a significant inertia that provoked a ripple effect. The experience has been followed by a series of artistic interventions that have been activating the ecosystem (territory-neighboring community), and have contributed to positioning the stream as the most visited ecological public park of the city. It truly empowered the community to replicate similar artistic interventions that created a virtuous circle.

One of the initial tangible effects was the significant reduction of quantity of tons of contaminating waste that the neighboring community was throwing into the stream. This has benefited the ecosystem's functioning, which in turn has a positive impact over all the population living downstream.

Later on, from February 16th to March 3rd, 2012, at Minimal-Arte, a local art gallery near 'Las Delicias' stream, an exhibition called 'Dialogues with Las Delicias Stream' was put up with all the artefacts that represented the creation of environmental awareness of 'Las Delicias' stream. The purpose of the exhibition was to engage other people of the neighborhoods that surrounded the stream to visit and promote the occurrence of future community artistic interventions, and further increase the environmental awareness among the population. The gallery exhibited the community children's drawings of the stream, the phrases they expressed to the Stream, a photo-slideshow, the recycled-material tree sculptures, and a trailer video-clip that documented the whole experience.

5 The artifacts that give dimension to the findings of this case study were also presented at the Lethaby Gallery in London on the 8th December 2011, as part of the 'MA Applied Imagination' research project that Santiago Aparicio V presented at Central Saint Martins School of Art and Design, University of the Arts London.

With the support of Conservation International, an additional campaign was conducted to invite crucial stakeholders from private and public sectors (environmental authorities) to the gallery in order to receive their feedback and engagement. This opened new doors for these kinds of interventions in Colombia and was a crucial step to promoting the process of replication of this experience through art techniques used at 'Las Delicias' stream.

Further on, on the 5th of May, 2012, the community leaders that have been empowered as eco-touristic guides (with the support of Conservation International), and organized the 'Carnavalito del Agua' (Little Water Carnival) where, through artistic and cultural activities, they engaged the local community to gain awareness on the valuable water stream that they have in their own neighborhood.

On the 27th of October, 2012, the local mayor of the area, the local community councils and other institutions (such as the environmental police), united to create a space that invited cultural collectives to an event called 'La Toma del Agua en la Quebrada' (drinking water from the stream) that promoted the conservation of the ecosystem. Art was again at the core of the planned activities and once again culture was used as a means to raise awareness.

During November 2012, the two institutions 'Sociedad Invisible Artistic Collective' and 'The Agency' united to design a project that reactivates 'Las Delicias' Stream's surroundings to a place 'full of colors'. For this purpose a festival was organized. On that day, more than 300 people enjoyed street food, performances, music, and face painting, and participated in a major photo shooting activity called 'The river of Colors' ('Río de Colores').

Then during the last quarter of 2013, a performance called 'Agua Quebrada' was executed, where the Foundation Naturaleza y Patrimonio, awarded with the Art and Nature Scholarship of the Distrital Institute of Arts — IDARTES 2013, made an artistic proposal that made visible the crystalline water surging from the east mountains and polluted during its path to the river mouth. Although the reach of this particular project was not restricted to 'Las Delicias' stream, it is worth mentioning its impact in all the east mountains of Bogotá, where 'Las Delicias' stream originates, along with other neighboring streams such as 'La Vieja'. It is worth highlighting the follow-

Figure 9. "Río de Colores" performance. Photo By: Oscar Filigrana

Figure 10. Stream's silhouette/course painting over Bogotá's financial street, 72nd street. Photo by: Carolina Cruz

ing components of this project: a 'Sensory capsule' of the East Mountains and 'La Vieja' stream, healing and reflection concerts, and hikes to the east mountains. This project had an artistic intervention in the street, where images of the forest reserve of the east mountains flora and fauna were presented, in addition to the interpretation of the riverbed of the stream 'La Vieja' through the road and sidewalks of the 72nd street.

One year after the artistic intervention occurred on September 2011, the following testimonies of crucial players in the community system demonstrated the structural changes that had been fostered through this process:

Sofía López, Comm-unityary Eco-touristic Guide:

A web has been threaded, a big goal was threading a strong environmental web. This facilitates communitarian strengthening. Some of the people that live near the stream keep being just neighbors not the stream, the ecosystem (...). People from around all the city are coming, the universities are engaged in the process, the NGOs, the public institutions, the schools... young people have been near the process when we gave them the possibility of being truly themselves [facilitating artistic and cultural spaces for them]. Through the community kitchen we have found possibilities of anchoring and reaching the community. At the beginning when I began climbing it [the mountain that hosts Las Delicias Stream] it was boring...I accepted the job as eco-touristic guide that International Conservation (CI) offered me because I needed the money...but now I have seen the splendour of the place...we miss valuable things in everyday life. I have learnt to admire myself through my work's mission. The process of restoration of the stream is the creation and un-covering of the identity of the place. (...) Changing behaviours is a long term task. (...) Bringing the kids to the stream again and developing artistic, cultural, ludic activities with them was crucial for achieving this whole change; they became sensitized and began taking stories to their parents. The neighboring adults then have really got engaged in the process and you can see them on the stream, it is all thanks to the children.

Patricia Bejarano, Coordinator of the Conservation International project:

The two things that created the change were: 1) Having the right communication strategy, and the right medium to engage the community (through art and culture), giving a place to each. 2) Really contributing to create a web, you meet me by chance, then you introduce me to others, others introduce themselves to others and so on, friendships have been created. Even a couple fell in love walking up the stream and mountains and now they are married. Academics, students, priests, public institutions are now engaged. The big achievement is that the inertia is now rolling on, and it does not need Conservation International as an indispensable engine anymore, it's now moving by itself.

Diana Aya, young community leader, who worked at Conservation International and is also an inhabitant of the 'Moraci' stream, nearby to 'Las Delicias':

The process developed around the streams from artistic expressions, has positioned as a necessary amalgam to join the technic and scientific restoration actions of the streams with the community dynamics. This by integrating diversity and making visible aspects that make more beautiful and makes them notorious and visible at specific moments, calling people to embrace natural spaces, giving time so that life's cycles can make their purpose, while time passes and a tree grows and birds fly, people embrace the streams and re-learn to understand them as a fundamental part of their environment, and therefore from their life. They turn in encounter spaces for enjoying, living together and for making conservation.

Andrés Plazas, Walker and Leader of the NGO 'Amigos de la Montaña':

In Las Delicias stream restoration process it has become evident that the problems associated with apparently dissimilar issues like environment, safety and community strengthening, that traditionally will be afforded through different disciplines (biology, safety experts-policemen and scientists), is really the same one thing. It's the enjoyment of the territory and its care, with the marvelous pretext of the encounter around art and culture that creates the weaving of social fabric. The green threads in the community a need for maturation/maturing, for its well being, with a strengthening of the identity and confidence that the same community is the one that can create the solutions to their own problems.

Octavio Rodríguez, a sociologist that works at Conservation International and has been the supporter of the community strategy over the restoration process of Las Delicias stream:

The impact of the artistic interventions and the culture of environmental awareness are evident in the quantity of positive comments that have arrived to CI signaling the importance of this project. This is also reflected in the lyrics of the hip-hop music of the community groups and artworks of the artists. [There has been] relevant coverage of mass media and alternative media of the cultural interventions, in addition to the incorporation of new social agents. Nowadays other institutions keep summing up to Las Delicias' initiative, such as Los Andes University, the Distrital University, SENA, Mesa Interlocal Río Salitre, and Veeduría Ciudadana de Bogotá.

As a consequence of these experiences, people are now actively discussing and arguing around the stream, which demonstrates the relevance that the ecosystem by itself is acquiring and its increased liveliness. This case study constituted a

new form of knowledge, not just because it raised the environmental awareness of the inhabitants of neighborhoods surrounding 'Las Delicias', but especially because it uncovered the key role that art, as a tool for creating emotional adaptation to climate change, may play in fostering this awareness. By involving people's emotions, this form of communication is likely to be more effective and long lasting than traditional environmental education, prohibitions, or restoration efforts.

Recognizing the value of their ecosystem, the value of the pure water that the 'Las Delicias' stream carries just beside their neighborhoods, how the water comes from the pristine higher mountains, and how it's a privilege having it, and consequently embracing the stream to take care of it, is the new way to connect to their territory. Seeing the extreme variability of water level that has existed in other places of the city helps them recognize the risk of experiencing similar phenomena. By reducing the level of waste thrown into the stream and by collaborating to recover native vegetation along the stream's bank, this process has achieved ecosystem recovery and increased resilience, thanks to the emotional preparedness and awareness of the radical changes that are occurring with climate variability. The agents have reduced their vulnerability while acquiring a new perception on the relation between the environment and the community.

In this example emotional adaptation, fostered through art and cultural identity strengthening, became a development tool that promoted conservation, ecosystem recovery, and at the same time increased the level of comprehension of the threat of climate change on the rational and imaginative levels. This comprehension is part of a real structural transformation, where the complex problems the community is facing are approached by other disciplines, giving place to deep social and environmental impacts. Shifting the egocentric paradigm that predominantly rules to an eco-centered paradigm has fostered the key foundations that are promoting the behavioral change that will hopefully lead to a more sustainable future.

EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION: A USEFUL CONCEPT FOR COMMUNITIES AND THE ENVIRONMENT

In the process of conducting this research, we have identified two possible ways to foster emotional adaptation: a) using 'cultural agency', where art and its symbols impact emotions and therefore serve as a medium; and b) strengthening local cultural identity with relation to the environment. These two alternatives are not mutually exclusive, and should both be accompanied by the promotion of direct physical contact and intimacy with nature, while acknowledging the power of nature to create a transformational process, which aids emotional and psychological healing to life's stressful events.

In the first case (using cultural agency) art has played a crucial role as a medium through which the psychological shift required for emotional adaptation was fostered. During the case study developed at 'Las Delicias' stream during Septem-

ber 2011 the collaborative community art installations functioned as a symbolic bridge between the community and the surrounding ecosystem. This 'dialogue' inspired a new understanding of the ecosystem as a living being. In that particular context, art, a new language connecting nature and the individuals, generated a new sense of belonging and environmental awareness about sustainability and the recovery of ecosystems.

Strengthening local cultural identity with relation to the environment (the second method identified) was at the same time a consequence of the enhanced cultural agency through art, and a means to multiply and erase inertia around a broader transformation rooted in a profound mind-shift in the community actors. The local actors' engagement with the artistic interventions was instrumental in re-creating a new local sense of identity. This was rooted in a new understanding of the role that the stream plays in their day-to-day lives, and the role that they, as agents of transformation, play with in the recovery and conservation of the stream.

Once communities recover and recognize through such a process of emotional adaptation that they play an active role in the systemic functioning of ecosystems and nature as a whole, they become more reflexive and conscious of their everyday actions and their impact over the system.

People are used to underestimating the value and beauty of those things that appear to be common to their everyday lives, taking them for granted. Nature and its components are not an exception to this, hence they become an additional element of the landscape that we tend to ignore. This contributes to deepening a disconnection between the community and the environment. Emotional adaptation processes can help to give a new meaning to the space where life takes place, placing the ecosystem and its elements at the core, with human communities as an integral part of a much broader system.

The case study showed the close relationship that exists between emotional adaptation and sustainability. The process of behavioral change that was fostered worked as an effective way to increase the awareness and understanding of climate change. It had direct impacts in the increased resilience of the community and the ecosystem. One of the most difficult issues over the behavioural change regarding environmental issues is that the environment is a collective asset where impacts are usually intangible, and where a perfect assignation of costs is virtually impossible. If people do not comprehend the complexity of the system, then themselves and their descendants will be directly affected.

Emotional adaptation poses as a suitable concept to develop and apply over public policy frameworks, as contributing to the creation of structural changes. These in turn can contribute to the establishment of a stronger relationship with the environment, which individuals feel an integral part of. This process of new understanding makes us realize that affecting the environment is equivalent to affecting one's self, and a process of transformation detonates. Structural behavioral changes must come from within, and should not be achieved

through indoctrination processes where green actions are acted without a reflexive process behind them. The community from the experiential and imaginative level is the one that can construct cultural changes that create a sustainable relation with the ecosystem.

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